

Description of Additional Supplementary Files

File name: Supplementary Data 1

Description: Source data for Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 7, and Figure 9.

File name: Supplementary Data 2

Description: Source data for Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 6.